

Particulate matter 2.5 pollution, perception, and mental stress

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ABSTRACT

Multivariate mediation analyses were used to relate perceptions of particulate matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}) pollution level directly and indirectly to mental stress of residents in Bangkok, Thailand. PM_{2.5} induced concerns about respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment served as mediators of the indirect effects. This study decomposed full perception into correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level) and misperception so that the effects of perception and its components can be examined separately. The data were daily time series, beginning July 30, 2016, and ending September 30, 2023. Unobserved perception, PM_{2.5} induced concerns, and mental stress were proxied by Google's relative search volume indexes. Correct perception was the actual PM_{2.5}, whereas misperception was the regression residual of the full perception on the actual PM_{2.5}. In the full sample, full perception and misperception had significant indirect effects, whereas correct perception had a significant direct effect. Respiratory disease was the main contributor to the significant indirect effect, although concern itself was not significant. For the COVID-19 subsample, full perceptions showed significant total, direct, and indirect effects. The significant indirect effect was explained by concerns regarding respiratory diseases and health. Correct perception had a significant direct effect; its indirect effect was small and nonsignificant. The results for misperceptions were similar to those for perceptions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The most significant environmental threat to public health worldwide is air pollution. Each year, pollution causes approximately 7 million premature deaths worldwide. Particulate matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}) has been identified as the most dangerous particle [1]. In terms of economic value, it was estimated, for example, in China to cost 1,388.8 and 897.7 Chinese yuan per person per year for health impacts and for depression, respectively [2]. PM_{2.5} refers to tiny particles or droplets in air with a width of ≤ 2.5 microns. The sources of PM_{2.5} pollution are industrial processes, combustion sources (e.g., electric utilities and vehicular exhausts), fugitive sources (e.g., construction and biomass burning), and natural sources (e.g., wind erosion and sea salt aerosols) [3], [4]. Different sources contribute to the different PM_{2.5} components, which in turn affect the levels of toxicity and health impacts. Such components include sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, chloride, elemental and organic carbon, crustal materials, and biological materials [3], [5].

PM_{2.5} has been linked to respiratory, cardiovascular, allergic, cerebrovascular, kidney, skin, and reproductive system diseases and diabetes [6]–[9]. Ultrafine PM_{2.5} particles deeply penetrate the lung wall [10]. Metabolic activation, oxidative stress and damage, mutagenicity and genotoxicity, inflammation, and immune

disorders are potential mechanisms underlying PM_{2.5} induced physical diseases [8], [9], [11]. PM_{2.5} can also cause mental diseases [12], [13]. The direct mechanism is through induction of systemic or brain-based oxidative stress and inflammation [14] as well as dysfunctional breathing and heart performance [15], [16]. Regarding indirect mechanisms, certain PM_{2.5} induced diseases, such as respiratory or cardiovascular diseases, lower work efficiency, and labor productivity [17], result in work stress, fear of unemployment, and poor mental health [18]. Mental stress increases if the PM_{2.5} level exceeds the human-adaptive capability [19], whereas studies [20], [21] have also reported mental stress from concerns or fears of PM_{2.5} induced diseases.

Mental health is one of the leading global health issues for 2023 [22]. Among the mental disorders, the prevalence of psychological distress at 50.0%, is followed by mental stress at 36.5% [23]. While the relationship between PM_{2.5} and mental health has been investigated extensively, few studies have investigated the relationship between PM_{2.5} and mental stress [24], [25]. Studies [20], [21] and [26] in China and the U.S., respectively, reported that mental stress has a significant relationship with PM_{2.5} level. A study on pregnant women in Korea [27] found similar results. Previous studies have consistently reported for Bangkok residents that PM_{2.5} was associated with respiratory diseases [28]–[30]; a negative correlation of PM_{2.5} with daily confirmed COVID-19 cases, was found during the COVID-19 pandemic period [31]. Finally, another study [29] linked cardiovascular diseases to pollution. Studies relating PM_{2.5} with mental diseases or physical diseases other than respiratory and cardiovascular diseases have not been conducted based on the Bangkok sample.

The effects of PM_{2.5} on mental stress can result from perceived [20], [21] or actual PM_{2.5} levels [26], [27]. It is important to note that the perception of PM_{2.5} levels can be decomposed into correct perception (or actual PM_{2.5} levels) and misperception. The objective of this study is to decompose this perception and use the results to examine the mechanism by which the perception and its components affect mental stress. The findings can be applied towards public health recommendations and risk communication [20]. The role of misperception in mental stress is a novel focus of this study. Misperception is measured using the regression residual of the perceived PM_{2.5} level on actual PM_{2.5} levels. The unobserved perception is proxied by the Google relative search volume index, which is both easy and inexpensive to collect. Endogeneity problems in the analyses, which can lead to biased and inconsistent estimates, are addressed using instrumental-variable regressions.

2. METHOD

2.1. Model

This study investigated the relationship between the perception of PM_{2.5} level and mental stress using multivariate mediation analysis [32], [33]. This relationship was both direct and indirect. Regarding the indirect relationship, concern about PM_{2.5} induced diseases and unwanted experiences 1 to N served as mediators. A path diagram of the analysis is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Path diagram of multivariate mediation analysis

Perception was the determining variable shown in Figure 1, left panel, whereas mental stress was the outcome. The aggregate relationship between the two variables is measured by the coefficient c . The direct relationship between the perception and mental stress is inferred from the coefficient c' in the right panel. This was estimated by controlling for the mediation variables. The coefficients a_1 to a_N indicate the relationship between perception and PM_{2.5}-induced concerns about 1–N. The relationship between concerns

and mental stress is represented by coefficients b_1 to b_N . Perceptions can be divided into correct and misperceptions. Thus, the perception in Figure 1 represents full, correct, or misperceptions in the analysis.

The total and direct effects were measured using the coefficients c and c' , respectively. Thus, the indirect effect equals $c - c'$, whose contributors are the concerns 1 to N . The study measures the contribution of concerns 1 to N using a_1b_1 to a_Nb_N , where $a_1b_1 + \dots + a_Nb_N = c - c'$ [33]. In this study, the concerns were limited to $N=4$, that is, respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment. These two diseases have significant health impacts on the Bangkok sample [28]–[30]. Respiratory diseases are of great concern to Bangkok residents [34]. These two diseases were common [6], [7], [35]–[37]. The toxicity and severity of $PM_{2.5}$ depend largely on its source and chemical composition [5]. These two factors are similar in Thailand [3], [38]–[42] and China [43]. In China, a study [35] concluded that respiratory and cardiovascular diseases are the most dangerous $PM_{2.5}$ induced diseases. Health concerns represented the perceived $PM_{2.5}$ induced health risks and diseases other than respiratory and cardiovascular diseases [20]. Unemployment is a non-health risk factor. It is induced by $PM_{2.5}$ pollution and is able to increase mental stress [18]. When N is 4, the total, direct, and indirect effects are c , c' , and $a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3 + a_4b_4$. Concerns 1 and 2 pertain to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, respectively. Concern 3 concerns health, whereas concern 4 concerns unemployment.

2.2. Data

This study employed time-series data. The sample consisted of residents of Bangkok, Thailand. The $PM_{2.5}$ level was daily. Bangkok's air quality index (AQI) was measured by the Pollution Control Department of Thailand's Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment. Daily Google relative search volume (RSV) indices proxy for the unobserved full perception of $PM_{2.5}$ level, concern about $PM_{2.5}$ induced diseases, and level of mental stress. RSV indices have become increasingly popular in medical and healthcare research [44], [45]. The RSV provides deep insights into individual behavior. Individuals actively relay information about their identities, thoughts, and behaviors when searching Google [46]; they search Google only for information they prefer [47]. Compared to cohort and survey data, RSV data are easy and inexpensive to collect. Because they are time-series data, short-term relationships such as daily relationships can be tested, whereas it is hardly possible to use cohort or survey data [48]. Air quality and RSV indices can be downloaded from certain websites at any time free of charge.

Thailand is an interesting country to study mental stress. A recent survey [49] reported that eight out of ten consumers had experienced mental health issues in the past six months, with mental stress accounting for the largest share (46%). Bangkok, Thailand's capital of 1,569 square kilometers in size and more than 14 million residents, was chosen as the sample city because it is one of the most $PM_{2.5}$ polluted cities. On April 15, 2023, Bangkok was among the top 10 worst cities in the world. It ranked 7th [50], whereas at the time of writing this study (October 24, 2023), its rank was 14th [51]. In Bangkok, the main outdoor sources of $PM_{2.5}$ are vehicular exhaust (43.7%), biomass burning (24.0%), sea salt aerosols (10.5%), power plants (6.48%), and industrial emissions (4.46%) [3]. The main indoor sources are cigarette smoking and charcoal stove cooking. Indoor and outdoor $PM_{2.5}$ levels are highly correlated [38]. The major chemical components of $PM_{2.5}$ are ammonium, black carbon, chromium, iron, manganese, nickel, nitrate, sulfate, and zinc [38]–[42]. A survey [52] conducted by Thailand's Department of Health revealed that 80% of respondents were concerned about the health effects of $PM_{2.5}$. In a recent survey [34] by Bangkok University, the respondents reported that they had cough and throat irritation (57.8%), sneezing, running nose, and nosebleed (51.6%), red eye and eye irritation (31.3%), allergies (29.1%), dyspnea and pneumonia (24.4%), and body rash (17.0%). They believed $PM_{2.5}$ was the cause of these symptoms.

The data began July 30, 2016, and ended September 30, 2023 (2,619 observations). Bangkok's $PM_{2.5}$ level was downloaded from the website of Air Quality Historical Data Platform. The date July 30, 2016 was chosen because it is the first day the $PM_{2.5}$ level was reported. Due to machine failure, routine maintenance, changes in the siting of monitors, and human error, some $PM_{2.5}$ observations were missing. This study imputed the missing observations using a linear interpolation method [53].

The unobserved perception of the level of $PM_{2.5}$ and concerns about diseases, health, and unemployment were specific to Bangkok. Following a study [54], the search query for the perception was "PM 2.5". Concern for respiratory and cardiovascular diseases and mental stress used the search queries "โรคทางเดินหายใจ" (*Rokh thāng dein hāyaci*, meaning respiratory diseases) [55], "โรคหลอดเลือดหัวใจ" (*Rokh hīlxdeūxd hāwaci*, meaning cardiovascular diseases) [56], and "เครียด" (*Kheriyd*, meaning stress) [57] in the Thai language, respectively. The query for the health concern was "สุขภาพ" (*Sūkhphāph*, meaning health) [58], whereas that for the unemployment was "ตกงาน" (*Tkngān*, meaning unemployed) [59]. The indices were downloaded from the Google Trends.

The average and standard deviation of the PM_{2.5} level were 81.693 and 1.195 AQI points, respectively. The RSV indices were relative. After scaling for the full sample, the maximum levels for the PM_{2.5} perception, concerns for respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment, and mental stress were 83.000, 1.800, 1.200, 100.000, 8.000, and 15.000 points, respectively, whereas the corresponding averages (standard deviations) were 1.643 (4.786), 0.061 (0.155), 0.056 (0.118), 54.163 (12.414), 0.950 (0.971), and 4.593 (1.730) points.

The PM_{2.5} level, and RSV indices exhibit trends and seasonal patterns [44], [60]. For this reason, all variables were de-trended and de-seasonalized by the logged time trend and day-of-week and month-of-year dummy variables. In the final step, the variables were standardized by their averages and standard deviations so that the sizes of the coefficients and effects could be compared.

Correct perception and misperception need be measured. In this study, the correct perception was the actual PM_{2.5} level. The misperception variable was the standardized regression residual of the “PM 2.5” RSV variable on the actual PM_{2.5} variable. All the resulting variables were stationary but non-normal, with a zero average and unit standard deviation. This study approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Thammasat University (Certificate of Approval No. 009/2566).

2.3. Statistical analysis

This study conducted three linear regressions for the multivariate mediation analysis. The first regression ran the perception variable on the mental stress variable to estimate the coefficient c to measure the total effect. The second regression considered the perception variables with the concern variables for respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment to test for the relationship a_1 to a_4 . The third regression regressed the mental stress variable on the perception variable and the four concern variables. The coefficients b_1 to b_4 from this regression indicate the effects of the concern variables, also serving as the regression’s control variables, on mental stress. The coefficient c' measured the direct effect of stress perception after controlling for concerns.rtc

It is likely that the three regressions suffer from endogeneity problems owing to omitted variables and errors in the variables [61]. This study is aware that other variables, such as health status and access to health care, could help to explain mental stress. But they are excluded from the analysis. An incomplete set of explanatory variables constitutes the omitted-variable problem. Moreover, perception, concerns, and mental stress cannot be observed. In analysis, these variables are proxied by Google RSVs. Alternative proxies, e.g. media coverage [62] and tweets [63], are possible; these proxies may encompass information on individual experiences and awareness the RSVs cannot capture. The fact that RSVs are proxies and cannot capture all the relevant information implies that the RSVs have measurement errors, thus leading to the errors-in-variables problem.

To mitigate these problems, this study used a generalized method of moments (GMM) regression [64]. The GMM is an instrumental variable (IV) regression technique that returns consistent, asymptotically normal, and efficient estimates even for non-normal variable specifications. The IVs were constructed using a two-step technique [65]. Pal’s IVs [66] were inputs in the first step. Statistical tests were performed based on the heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent standard deviation [67]. The standard deviations for the individual and aggregate indirect effects were computed using this method [33]. All estimations and tests were processed using the statistical program EViews version 9.5 (IHS Global, Inc.).

3. RESULTS

This study estimated the coefficients of the multivariate mediation model in Figure 1 and used them to compute the direct and indirect effects of full perception, correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level), and misperception on mental stress. The indirect effect is the sum of the four components resulting from concerns about respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment. In this study, significance corresponds with a p-value of 0.05 or lower. (The coefficient estimates are not shown. These data are available from the corresponding author upon request.).

3.1. Full sample

Table 1 presents the results for the entire sample. Column 2 shows that the total effect of full perception was not significant. The direct effect was negative but not significant, whereas the indirect effect was positive and significant. The indirect effect was significantly larger than the direct effect. The total effect was the sum of the direct and indirect effects. Thus, it is likely that the non-significance results from the fact that the direct and indirect effects cancel each other. The sum of the effects of the four concerns was a significant indirect effect. Respiratory diseases contributed to 47.83% of the indirect effects. Although not significant, its p-value was low (0.091).

This study decomposed full perception into correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level) and misperception components. The shares of these two components were 2.27% and 97.73%, respectively. Despite its much smaller share, correct perception has a greater influence on mental stress than misperception. From the regression analysis, the R² coefficient of correct perception was 0.009, compared with the 0.001 R² coefficient of misperception.

Table 1. Effects of perception of PM_{2.5} level on mental stress for the full sample (July 30, 2016 to September 30, 2023)

Effect	Full perception	Components of perception	
		Actual PM _{2.5} level, correct perception	Misperception
Total effect (<i>c</i>)	0.019	0.099	-0.007
Direct effect (<i>c'</i>)	-0.005	0.090*	-0.028
Indirect effect ($c - c' = a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3 + a_4b_4$)	0.024*	0.010	0.021*
(1) Respiratory diseases (a_1b_1)	0.011	0.010*	0.009
(2) Cardiovascular diseases (a_2b_2)	0.002	0.001	0.002
(3) Health (a_3b_3)	0.005	-0.002	0.005
(4) Unemployment (a_4b_4)	0.005	0.001	0.005

* $p \leq 0.05$.

Column 3 of Table 1 reports the effects of the correct perception. The direct effect is statistically significant. It is eight times larger than the indirect effect. Concern about respiratory diseases was the largest contributor to the indirect effect, and it was significant. However, summing this with the remaining three concerns constitutes the indirect effect, which was not significant. Column 4 of Table 1 reports the results for misperception. As misperception explains most perceptions, their effects on mental stress are very similar.

3.2. COVID-19 subsample

COVID-19 has caused a global pandemic. To contain spread of the disease, quarantines have been imposed in almost all capitals and major cities worldwide, resulting in a significant improvement in air quality. The average reduction in PM_{2.5} pollution was 12% [68]. When PM_{2.5} pollution fell, mental stress rose [69]. Thailand and its capital Bangkok experienced the same situations [70], [71]. This study examined the effects of the COVID-19 period to gain insights into the contribution of falling PM_{2.5} level and rising mental stress. The COVID-19 subsample began on April 3, 2020, and ended on September 30, 2022) [72]. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effects of perception of PM_{2.5} level on mental stress for the COVID-19 subsample (April 3, 2020 to September 30, 2022)

Effect	Full perception	Components of perception	
		Actual PM _{2.5} level, correct perception	Misperception
Total effect (<i>c</i>)	0.228*	0.121*	0.159*
Direct effect (<i>c'</i>)	0.157*	0.104*	0.090
Indirect effect ($c - c' = a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3 + a_4b_4$)	0.071*	0.017	0.069*
(1) Respiratory diseases (a_1b_1)	0.019*	0.001	0.018*
(2) Cardiovascular diseases (a_2b_2)	0.000	0.000	0.000
(3) Health (a_3b_3)	0.035*	0.007	0.037*
(4) Unemployment (a_4b_4)	0.017	0.009	0.013

* $p \leq 0.05$.

Column 2 of Table 2 shows that the total, direct, and indirect effects of the full perceptions are significant. For the indirect effect, the significant components were concerns about respiratory diseases and health. Health concerns were almost two times that of respiratory diseases. In the COVID-19 subsample, full perception was composed of 11.91% correct perception, whereas misperception had an 88.09% share. The explanatory abilities of the two components were approximately the same. Their R² coefficients of the regressions for mental stress were 0.012 and 0.010, respectively. Column 3 of Table 2 reports the effects of correct perception. The total and direct effects are statistically significant. The indirect effect and its four components were not statistically significant. Finally, column 4 of Table 2 shows that the total effect of misperception is significant. The significant result was from the indirect effect, whose significant components were concerns about respiratory diseases and health. This result was similar to that of the full perceptions.

4. DISCUSSION

The perceived and actual levels of PM_{2.5} affect mental stress [20], [27]. Previous studies [20] based on perceived PM_{2.5} levels did not distinguish whether the relationship was from the actual level (correct perception) or misperception. One study Chen *et al.* [73] acknowledged that decomposition is difficult; therefore, the sources of the effects could not be identified. This study was able to unbundle the perceived level into the actual level and misperceptions.

This study decomposes full perception into correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level) and misperception components, so that the effects of perception, actual PM_{2.5} level, and misperception can be measured and tested separately. Concerns about health risks in previous studies [20], [21], which served as mediators, were general. In this study, concerns about specific PM_{2.5} induced diseases were considered, together with health risks. Unemployment was included as a mediation variable. Concern about unemployment due to PM_{2.5} pollution is possible [18].

Most epidemiological studies on the relationship between PM_{2.5} and mental health have chosen cohort or survey data [24], [25]. Obtaining a sufficient number of participants and covering a long observation period for a cohort or survey study is costly and time-consuming [48]. Although individual-level data are accurate and preferred, benefits relate to the ways in which the data are included in the analyses [74]. Moreover, questionnaire responses tend to suffer from unreliability and measurement errors [75].

In this study, tests were conducted based on daily observations. The finding that these effects are significant indicates that they materialize on the day of exposure to pollution. The immediate effects found in this study are consistent with those in a Paris study [76], in which PM_{2.5} effects on mental stress were immediate and short-term, within one day. This contradicts the results of the Nanjing study [20], which found no evidence to support the direct effect of real-time PM_{2.5} exposure. The different conclusions of this study and the Paris study [76] from the Nanjing study [20] regarding the immediacy of the effects can be explained by the sample used. While the former used daily time-series data, the latter used survey data.

For the full sample and COVID-19 subsample, the significant effect for perception is consistent with other studies [20], whereas the significant effects for correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level) is also supported by a previous report [27]. In this study, the significant results for the correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level) are explained by the direct effect. This finding supports the fact that PM_{2.5} toxicity, and human responses link actual PM_{2.5} level directly with mental stress [14]–[16]. However, this does not support the findings of the study by Liu *et al.* [20], which did not find any direct effect. Liu *et al.* [20] argued that the mental stress was “subjected to the indirect influence of physical symptoms, by increasing perceived effect on health and increasing attribution to indoor pollution sources.”

There was a significant indirect effect of misperception on mental stress. Its direct effect is non-significant. This study found that misperception accounted for 97.73% and 88.09% of the perception of the full sample and COVID-19 subsample, respectively. Moreover, Chen *et al.* [77] reported that the respondents' perception of PM_{2.5} levels depended on factors such as age, education level, family income, and history of respiratory diseases. The perception is likely to be a misperception. Misperception has no direct relationship with mental stress [14]–[16]. This indirect effect was mediated by PM_{2.5} induced concerns [20].

The indirect effect was the sum of the four PM_{2.5} induced concerns. In the full sample for misperception, concerns about respiratory diseases explained most of the significant indirect effects. Its share was 42.86%, whereas the remaining concerns regarding cardiovascular diseases, health, and unemployment were 9.52%, 23.81%, and 23.81%, respectively. None of these concerns were significant. Limited awareness of PM_{2.5} and other pollutants, and associated diseases and health problems was also found in an early study in the United Kingdom [78].

The significance of the concerns linked to indirect effects is more pronounced for the COVID-19 subsample. Significant concerns included respiratory diseases and health. Cardiovascular diseases and unemployment were not found to be significant concerns. Despite a low PM_{2.5} pollution level in the COVID-19 subsample [70], the significant PM_{2.5} induced concern of respiratory diseases is supported by a study [79] that found that public interest, measured by Google RSV indexes, significantly increased during the COVID-19 period. Saeed *et al.* [80] reported that COVID-19 increased individual and public health awareness. Bangkok residents revealed their health awareness and its relationship with COVID-19 and PM_{2.5} pollution in a survey [52].

The sample comprises Bangkok residents and their perception of PM_{2.5}. Different PM_{2.5} sources in various areas contribute varying levels and types of toxic components. Thus, health impacts and risk perception vary among cities [81]. Perception is influenced by residents' exposure to environmental news and media coverage, shaping their knowledge about air pollution [82], whereas such news and coverage are highly localized [83]. Finally, perception is not solely dependent on the actual PM_{2.5} level; other factors such as health infrastructure also play significant roles [84]. Therefore, the findings of this study are confined to Bangkok, Thailand, and may not be universally applicable to other cities or countries.

5. CONCLUSION

Multivariate mediation analysis was used to examine the total, direct, and indirect relationship of the perception of PM_{2.5} level on mental stress for Bangkok residents. The effects on mental health are significant. A direct effect was caused by correct perception (actual PM_{2.5} level). Misperception had an indirect effect, in which concerns about respiratory diseases and health were significant mediators. Although the literature points to the importance of cardiovascular diseases and possible job displacement, residents are unaware of the potential threats. After the COVID-19 outbreak ended and economic activities returned to normal, PM_{2.5} pollution started to increase. Regulators must closely monitor PM_{2.5} pollution levels, and strictly control emissions from the main sources. Additionally, it is important to raise public awareness that PM_{2.5} induced diseases are not limited to the respiratory system. Serious diseases such as cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and even kidney or reproductive diseases are possible. Perception varies among cities and countries, meaning that the effects of PM_{2.5} on mental stress and the mediating factors involved can vary significantly. Results from different cities and countries are intriguing, suggesting the need for comparative studies in future research.

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REFERENCES

- [1] United Nation Environment Programme, "Pollution action note — data you need to know." Accessed: Jun. 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unep.org/interactives/air-pollution-note/#:~:text=Pollution Action Note – Data you, million premature deaths every year>
- [2] H. Yin, M. Pizzol, J. B. Jacobsen, and L. Xu, "Contingent valuation of health and mood impacts of PM_{2.5} in Beijing, China," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 630, pp. 1269–1282, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.02.275.
- [3] C. Choochuay *et al.*, "Impacts of PM_{2.5} sources on variations in particulate chemical compounds in ambient air of Bangkok, Thailand," *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 1657–1667, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.apr.2020.06.030.
- [4] C. S. Liang, F. K. Duan, K. Bin He, and Y. L. Ma, "Review on recent progress in observations, source identifications, and countermeasures of PM_{2.5}," *Environment International*, vol. 86, pp. 150–170, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2015.10.016.
- [5] W. Zhou *et al.*, "Exposure scenario: Another important factor determining the toxic effects of PM_{2.5} and possible mechanisms involved," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 226, pp. 412–425, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2017.04.010.
- [6] W. R. Wan Mahiyuddin, R. Ismail, N. Mohammad Sham, N. I. Ahmad, and N. M. N. Nik Hassan, "Cardiovascular and respiratory health effects of fine particulate matters (PM_{2.5}): A review on time series studies," *Atmosphere*, vol. 14, no. 5, 2023, doi: 10.3390/atmos14050856.
- [7] S. Sharma, M. Chandra, and S. H. Kota, "Health effects associated with PM_{2.5}: A systematic review," *Current Pollution Reports*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 345–367, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40726-020-00155-3.
- [8] W. Xu *et al.*, "The influence of PM_{2.5} exposure on kidney diseases," *Human and Experimental Toxicology*, vol. 41, pp. 1–9, 2022, doi: 10.1177/09603271211069982.
- [9] M. J. Piao *et al.*, "Particulate matter 2.5 damages skin cells by inducing oxidative stress, subcellular organelle dysfunction, and apoptosis," *Archives of Toxicology*, vol. 92, no. 6, pp. 2077–2091, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s00204-018-2197-9.
- [10] W. Xie, J. You, C. Zhi, and L. Li, "The toxicity of ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) to vascular endothelial cells," *Journal of Applied Toxicology*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 713–723, 2021, doi: 10.1002/jat.4138.
- [11] S. Feng *et al.*, "The pathophysiological and molecular mechanisms of atmospheric PM_{2.5} affecting cardiovascular health: A review," *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, vol. 249, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.114444.
- [12] Z. Yang *et al.*, "Air pollution and mental health: The moderator effect of health behaviors," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 16, no. 4, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/abe88f.
- [13] J. D. King, S. Zhang, and A. Cohen, "Air pollution and mental health: Associations, mechanisms, and methods," *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 192–199, 2022, doi: 10.1097/YCO.0000000000000771.
- [14] J. Song *et al.*, "Microglial activation and oxidative stress in PM_{2.5}-induced neurodegenerative disorders," *Antioxidants*, vol. 11, no. 8, 2022, doi: 10.3390/antiox11081482.
- [15] C. Spitzer *et al.*, "Mental health problems, obstructive lung disease, and lung function: Findings from the general population," *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 174–179, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jpsychores.2011.03.005.
- [16] A. M. Yohannes, T. G. Willgoss, R. C. Baldwin, and M. J. Connolly, "Depression and anxiety in chronic heart failure and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: Prevalence, relevance, clinical implications, and management principles," *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, vol. 25, no. 12, pp. 1209–1221, 2010, doi: 10.1002/gps.2463.
- [17] J. He, H. Liu, and A. Salvo, "Severe air pollution and labor productivity: Evidence from industrial towns in China," *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 173–201, 2019, doi: 10.1257/app.20170286.
- [18] Bilal, E. Mohammed Al-Matari, S. Khan, N. Ahmed Mareai Senan, A. Abbas, and S. Manzoor, "Impact of fear of COVID-19 pandemic on job insecurity and subjective well-being," *Inquiry (United States)*, vol. 59, pp. 1–12, 2022, doi: 10.1177/00469580221102695.
- [19] S. Cohen, D. Janicki-Deverts, and G. E. Miller, "Psychological stress and disease," *Jama*, vol. 298, no. 14, pp. 1685–1687, 2007, doi: 10.1001/jama.298.14.1685.
- [20] L. Liu, Y. Yan, N. Nazhalati, A. Kuerban, J. Li, and L. Huang, "The effect of PM_{2.5} exposure and risk perception on the mental stress of Nanjing citizens in China," *Chemosphere*, vol. 254, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.126797.
- [21] J. Li, L. Huang, B. Han, T. J. van der Kuip, Y. Xia, and K. Chen, "Exposure and perception of PM_{2.5} pollution on the mental stress of pregnant women," *Environment International*, vol. 156, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106686.

- [22] C. Annie, "11 global health issues to watch in 2023, according to IHME experts," *Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation*, 2023.
- [23] S. Nochaiwong *et al.*, "Global prevalence of mental health issues among the general population during the coronavirus disease-2019 pandemic: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-89700-8.
- [24] I. Braithwaite, S. Zhang, J. B. Kirkbride, D. P. J. Osborn, and J. F. Hayes, "Air pollution (particulate matter) exposure and associations with depression, anxiety, bipolar, psychosis and suicide risk: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Environmental Health Perspectives*, vol. 127, no. 12, 2019, doi: 10.1289/EHP4595.
- [25] T. Trushna, V. Dhiman, D. Raj, and R. R. Tiwari, "Effects of ambient air pollution on psychological stress and anxiety disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis of epidemiological evidence," *Reviews on Environmental Health*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 501–521, 2021, doi: 10.1515/reveh-2020-0125.
- [26] A. J. Mehta *et al.*, "Associations between air pollution and perceived stress: The veterans administration normative aging study," *Environmental Health: A Global Access Science Source*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2015, doi: 10.1186/1476-069X-14-10.
- [27] D. K. Lamichhane *et al.*, "Association between ambient air pollution and perceived stress in pregnant women," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-02845-4.
- [28] N. Vichit-Vadakan *et al.*, "Air pollution and respiratory symptoms: Results from three panel studies in Bangkok, Thailand," *Environmental Health Perspectives*, vol. 109, no. 3, pp. 381–387, 2001, doi: 10.2307/3434785.
- [29] N. R. Fold *et al.*, "An assessment of annual mortality attributable to ambient PM_{2.5} in Bangkok, Thailand," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 19, pp. 1–14, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17197298.
- [30] R. Onchang, K. Hirunkasi, and S. Janchay, "Establishment of a city-based index to communicate air pollution-related health risks to the public in Bangkok, Thailand," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 24, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su142416702.
- [31] S. Sangkham *et al.*, "Effects of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and meteorological factors on the daily confirmed cases of COVID-19 in Bangkok during 2020–2021, Thailand," *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, vol. 8, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cscee.2023.100410.
- [32] O. Y. Chén, C. Crainiceanu, E. L. Ogburn, B. S. Caffo, T. D. Wager, and M. A. Lindquist, "High-dimensional multivariate mediation with application to neuroimaging data," *Biostatistics*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 121–136, 2018, doi: 10.1093/biostatistics/kxx027.
- [33] D. P. MacKinnon, "Contrasts in multiple mediator models," *Substance Use Research: New Methods for New Questions*, pp. 141–160, 2000.
- [34] Prachatai, "Bangkok poll results: Most of them, 53.6%, are most concerned about PM_{2.5} dust." (in Thai), Accessed: Jun. 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://prachatai.com/journal/2023/03/103233>
- [35] F. Lu *et al.*, "Systematic review and meta-analysis of the adverse health effects of ambient PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ pollution in the Chinese population," *Environmental Research*, vol. 136, pp. 196–204, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2014.06.029.
- [36] J. Chen and G. Hoek, "Long-term exposure to PM and all-cause and cause-specific mortality: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Environment International*, vol. 143, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.105974.
- [37] J. Qi *et al.*, "Pollutant exposure and health outcomes: Protocol for a comprehensive umbrella review of meta-analyses and evidence mapping," *Toxicology Advances*, vol. 3, no. 3, 2021, doi: 10.53388/ATR2021080802.
- [38] F. C. Tsai, K. R. Smith, N. Vichit-Vadakan, B. D. Ostro, L. G. Chestnut, and N. Kungskulniti, "Indoor/outdoor PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Bangkok, Thailand," *Journal of Exposure Analysis and Environmental Epidemiology*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 15–26, 2000, doi: 10.1038/sj.jea.7500071.
- [39] W. Wimolwattanapun, P. K. Hopke, and P. Pongkiatkul, "Source apportionment and potential source locations of PM_{2.5} and PM_{2.5-10} at residential sites in metropolitan Bangkok," *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 172–181, 2011, doi: 10.5094/APR.2011.022.
- [40] P. Thammasaroj and W. Jinsart, "Effects of overcrowded traffic and road construction activities in bangkok on PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and heavy metal composition," *EnvironmentAsia*, vol. 12, pp. 28–35, 2019, doi: 10.14456/ea.2019.60.
- [41] M. Ahmad *et al.*, "Chemical composition, sources, and health risk assessment of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in urban sites of Bangkok, Thailand," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 21, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph192114281.
- [42] T. Rattanapontan *et al.*, "Secondary sources of PM_{2.5} based on the vertical distribution of organic carbon, elemental carbon, and water-soluble ions in Bangkok," *Environmental Advances*, vol. 11, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envadv.2022.100337.
- [43] D. Y. H. Pui, S. C. Chen, and Z. Zuo, "PM_{2.5} in China: Measurements, sources, visibility and health effects, and mitigation," *Particulology*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–26, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.partic.2013.11.001.
- [44] A. Mavragani, G. Ochoa, and K. P. Tsagarakis, "Assessing the methods, tools, and statistical approaches in Google Trends research: Systematic review," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 20, no. 11, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.2196/jmir.9366.
- [45] V. S. Arora, M. McKee, and D. Stuckler, "Google trends: Opportunities and limitations in health and health policy research," *Health Policy*, vol. 123, no. 3, pp. 338–341, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2019.01.001.
- [46] G. Eysenbach, "Infodemiology and infoveillance: Tracking online health information and cyberbehavior for public health," *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, vol. 40, pp. 154–158, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.amepre.2011.02.006.
- [47] Z. Da, J. Engelberg, and P. Gao, "In search of attention," *The Journal of Finance*, vol. 66, no. 5, pp. 1461–1499, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-6261.2011.01679.x.
- [48] N. Englert, "Fine particles and human health - a review of epidemiological studies," *Toxicology Letters*, vol. 149, no. 1–3, pp. 235–242, 2004, doi: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2003.12.035.
- [49] The Nation, "Mintel: About 8 in 10 Thais experience mental health issues, with Gen Zs feeling the loneliest." Accessed: Jun. 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationthailand.com/pr-news/business/40018422>
- [50] The Nation, "Bangkok joins Chiang Mai on list of 10 cities with worst air." Accessed: Jun. 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationthailand.com/thailand/general/40026688>
- [51] "Live most polluted major city ranking." IQAir, Accessed: Oct. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iqair.com/th-en/world-air-quality-ranking>.
- [52] Hfocus, "Survey of PM_{2.5} dust" (in Thai), Accessed: Jun. 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hfocus.org/content/2021/12/23884>
- [53] N. M. Noor, M. M. Al Bakri Abdullah, A. S. Yahaya, and N. A. Ramli, "Comparison of linear interpolation method and mean method to replace the missing values in environmental data set," *Materials Science Forum*, vol. 803, pp. 278–281, 2015, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.803.278.

- [54] W. Nazar and K. Plata-Nazar, "Changes in air pollution-related behaviour measured by google trends search volume index in response to reported air quality in Poland," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 21, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph182111709.
- [55] D. Mitra, S. R. Koti, P. A. Verma, and S. Saran, "Environmental risk factor assessment for major respiratory disorders in metropolitan cities of India using VIIRS Suomi Aerosol data and Google trends," *Environmental Sustainability*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 851–860, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s42398-021-00210-9.
- [56] C. Senecal, M. Mahowald, L. Lerman, F. Lopes-Jimenez, and A. Lerman, "Increasing utility of Google trends in monitoring cardiovascular disease," *Digital Health*, vol. 7, p. 1–9, 2021, doi: 10.1177/20552076211033420.
- [57] A. Brodeur, A. E. Clark, S. Fleche, and N. Powdthavee, "COVID-19, lockdowns and well-being: Evidence from Google trends," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, vol. 193, 2021, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3596670.
- [58] D. J. Callaghan, "Use of Google trends to examine interest in Mohs micrographic surgery: 2004 to 2016," *Dermatologic Surgery*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 186–192, 2018, doi: 10.1097/DSS.0000000000001270.
- [59] G. Caperna, M. Colagrossi, A. Geraci, and G. Mazzarella, "A babel of web-searches: Googling unemployment during the pandemic," *Labour Economics*, vol. 74, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.labeco.2021.102097.
- [60] N. Zhao, Y. Liu, J. K. Vanos, and G. Cao, "Day-of-week and seasonal patterns of PM_{2.5} concentrations over the United States: Time-series analyses using the prophet procedure," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 192, pp. 116–127, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.08.050.
- [61] J. M. Chen, M. Zovko, N. Šimurina, and V. Zovko, "Fear in a handful of dust: The epidemiological, environmental, and economic drivers of death by PM_{2.5} pollution," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 16, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18168688.
- [62] S. Chemli, M. Toanoglou, and M. Valeri, "The impact of COVID-19 media coverage on tourist's awareness for future travelling," *Current Issues in Tourism*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 179–186, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1080/13683500.2020.1846502.
- [63] P. Diddi and L. K. Lundy, "Organizational Twitter use: Content analysis of tweets during breast cancer awareness month," *Journal of Health Communication*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 243–253, 2017, doi: 10.1080/10810730.2016.1266716.
- [64] L. P. Hansen, "Large sample properties of generalized method of moment's estimators," *Econometrica*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 1029–1054, 1982, doi: 10.2307/1912775.
- [65] F. É. Racicot and R. Théoret, "Optimal instrumental variables generators based on improved Hausman regression, with an application to hedge fund returns," *Journal of Wealth Management*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 103–123, 2010, doi: 10.3905/JWM.2010.13.1.103.
- [66] N. P. Company, "Consistent moment estimators of regression coefficients in the presence of errors in variables," *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 349–364, 1980.
- [67] W. K. Newey and K. D. West, "A simple, positive semi-definite, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation consistent covariance matrix," *Econometrica*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 703–708, May 1987, doi: 10.2307/1913610.
- [68] D. Rodríguez-Urrego and L. Rodríguez-Urrego, "Air quality during the COVID-19: PM_{2.5} analysis in the 50 most polluted capital cities in the world," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 266, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115042.
- [69] J. Xiong *et al.*, "Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on mental health in the general population: A systematic review," *Journal of Affective Disorders*, vol. 277, pp. 55–64, 2020.
- [70] P. Wetchayont, "Investigation on the impacts of COVID-19 lockdown and influencing factors on air quality in greater Bangkok, Thailand," *Advances in Meteorology*, 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/6697707.
- [71] P. Mongkhon *et al.*, "Exposure to COVID-19-related information and its association with mental health problems in Thailand: Nationwide, cross-sectional survey study," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 23, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.2196/25363.
- [72] A. Khanthavit and S. Khanthavit, "ChatGPT and stress," *ABAC Journal*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 213–224, 2023, doi: 10.59865/abacj.2023.39.
- [73] S. Chen, P. Oliva, and P. Zhang, "Air pollution and mental health: Evidence from China," *AEA Papers and Proceedings*, vol. 114, pp. 423–428, 2024, doi: 10.1257/pandp.20241062.
- [74] W. R.E. and R. A.C., "Long-term particulate matter exposure: Attributing health effects to individual PM components," *Journal of the Air and Waste Management Association*, vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 523–543, 2015, doi: 10.1080/10962247.2015.1020396.
- [75] M. K. Chen, "Retrospective studies with survey data: Problems in social science and epidemiology research," *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 131–133, 1986, doi: 10.1016/0038-0121(86)90002-9.
- [76] B. Pignon *et al.*, "PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ air pollution peaks are associated with emergency department visits for psychotic and mood disorders," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 29, no. 59, pp. 88577–88586, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11356-022-21964-7.
- [77] Q. Chen, J. Zhang, Y. Xu, H. Sun, and Z. Ding, "Associations between individual perceptions of PM_{2.5} pollution and pulmonary function in Chinese middle-aged and elderly residents," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 20, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12889-020-08713-6.
- [78] K. Smallbone, "Individuals' interpretation of air quality information," School of Environment and Technology University of Brighton, pp. 1–56, 2012.
- [79] M. T. Barbosa, M. Morais-Almeida, C. S. Sousa, and J. Bousquet, "The 'Big Five' lung diseases in COVID-19 pandemic – a Google Trends analysis," *Pulmonology*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 71–72, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.pulmoe.2020.06.008.
- [80] B. Q. Saeed, I. Elbarazi, M. Barakat, A. O. Adrees, and K. S. Fahady, "COVID-19 health awareness among the United Arab Emirates population," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 16, no. 9, 2021, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0255408.
- [81] A. D. Bergstra, B. Brunekreef, and A. Burdorf, "The mediating role of risk perception in the association between industry-related air pollution and health," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 13, no. 5, 2018.
- [82] Y. Chen and X. Liu, "How do environmental news and the Under the Dome documentary influence air-pollution knowledge and risk perception among Beijing residents?" *SAGE Open*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.1177/21582440211015712.
- [83] W. Hong, Y. Wei, and S. Wang, "Left behind in perception of air pollution? A hidden form of spatial injustice in China," *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 666–684, 2022, doi: 10.1177/23996544211036145.
- [84] F. A. Armah, S. A. Boamah, R. Quansah, S. Obiri, and I. Luginah, "Unsafe occupational health behaviors: Understanding mercury-related environmental health risks to artisanal gold miners in Ghana," *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, vol. 4, no. 29, 2016, doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2016.00029.

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